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Chemical Examination of the Leaves of

Rhus mysurensis

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THE present paper deals with the study of complex mixture of flavonoids in the leaves extract of *Rhus mysurensis* (Anacardiaceae) procured from the Government Botanical Garden, Ooty (India). While the work was in progress, Sarada and Adinarayana¹ reported the isolation of kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin, hinokiflavone and 3-*O*-rhamnosides of myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol from the leaves of the same species. Our investigations revealed the presence of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone in addition to hinokiflavone, quercetin and kaempferol besides quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside, quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside.

The acetone extract of defatted leaves of *R. mysurensis* showed four distinct spots on tlc examination (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5). They were labelled as RM-I to RM-IV and separated by preparative tlc (B-P-F).

RM-I, on methylation was found to be a mixture of three methyl ethers. The two methyl ethers, m.p. 228-29° and 302° were characterised as hexamethyl ethers of amentoflavone² and cupressuflavone³, respectively by their nmr spectral studies; the third methyl ether, m.p. 202°, could not be characterised due to paucity of material.

RM-II, on derivatisation gave a pentacetate, m.p. 240° and a methyl ether, m.p. 260°. It was characterised as hinokiflavone⁴ by comparison of nmr spectra of its acetate and methyl ether with that of an authentic sample. RM-III, m.p. 314°, and RM-IV, m.p. 278° were characterised as quercetin and kaempferol on the basis of uv and nmr spectral studies⁵.

The methanol extract of acetone exhausted leaves on tlc examination (ethyl acetate-ethyl methyl ketone-acetic acid-water, 5 : 3 : 1 : 1) showed three major brown spots under uv light. They were separated by preparative tlc and labelled as RMG-I to RMG-III. All the three compounds gave positive Molisch and Shinoda tests indicating all to be flavonoidic glycosides.

RMG-I, m.p. 231-33°, on acid hydrolysis gave quercetin (m.p. 314°) and glucose. Uv spectral studies of the glucoside showed attachment of the sugar at C-3-hydroxyl of the aglycone. The final confirmation of the sugar attachment was obtained by the identification of partial methyl ether (m.p. 193°) obtained on hydrolysis of methylated glycoside⁶. The RMG-I was therefore identified as quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside. Similarly, RMG-II, m.p. 181-83°, and RMG-III, m.p. 178°, were identified as quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoside and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside⁷, respectively.

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Occurrence of Aurentiacin in

Didymocarpus podocarpa

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PHYTOCHEMICAL investigation on two *Didymocarpus* species, *D. pedicellata* and *D. aurentiaca* led to the isolation of a number of chalcones¹, quinochalcones², flavanones³, terpenoids⁴ and α -pyrones⁵. Recently, three kaurenoid diterpenes have been reported from another *Didymocarpus* sp., *D. oblonga*⁶. Very recently, one α -pyrone derivative, 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain has also been found to occur in *D. podocarpa*⁷.

Extraction of the whole plant of *D. podocarpa* with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) led to the isolation of a compound, m.p. 141° which was crystallised as orange plates (petroleum ether-benzene) and

analysed for $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ (M^+ 298). The uv spectrum

1

showed only one maximum at 343 nm. The ir spectrum revealed the presence of a chelated carbonyl function (1615 cm^{-1}), a complex aromatic substitution pattern ($1600, 1550, 1125, 745$ and 790 cm^{-1}) and a monosubstituted benzene ring (700 cm^{-1}). The nmr spectrum (60 MHz) δ 7.7 (2H, s, α - and β -protons), 14.06 (1H, s, disappeared on D_2O exchange, chelated phenolic-OH), 2.06 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 3.95 (3H, s, one- OCH_3), 4.0 (3H, s, one- OCH_3), 7.43 (5H, m, $5 \times ArH$), 6.03 (1H, s, ArH) showed resemblance with that of aurentiacin. The mass spectrum of this compound m/z 298 (M^+), 297 (M^+-1), 221 (M^+-77 , loss of phenyl nucleus) and 195 (M^+-103 , loss of styrene fragment), was also in accord with aurentiacin (2'-hydroxy-4',6'-dimethoxy-3'-methyl chalcone). Finally, this compound was identified as aurentiacin by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹ (m.m p., co-tlc and super imposable ir spectrum).

The occurrence of aurentiacin (1) is being reported for first time from *D. podocara*.

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Extraction and AAS Determination of Trace Amount of Cobalt in Medicinal Samples

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IN continuation of our work¹, the present communication reports a rapid method of determination of cobalt by AAS after its extraction with a β -diketo liquid chelating exchanger (LCE, $RCOCH_2COCF_3$, with $R=C_9H_{19}$) in chloroform as diluent. The method has been applied in the determination of cobalt in medicinal samples.

Experimental

LCE was prepared in two steps¹ starting from the parent compound, a C_{10} -isomeric monocarboxylic acid, Versatic-10 (Shell Chemical Co, London); a 0.1 M solution in chloroform was used in the present work. A solution of Co^{II} was prepared by dissolving $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ (Sarabhai Chemicals) in double-distilled water and was standardised complexometrically². All other reagents used were of analytical grade or comparable purity.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer with the following conditions: cobalt hollow cathode lamp current, 9 mA; burner height, 6 mm; wavelength, 240.7 nm; slit width, 1.9 Å; air flow rate, 10 $dm^3\text{ min}^{-1}$; acetylene flow rate, 2.5 $dm^3\text{ min}^{-1}$; working concentration range, 2.5–10.0 ppm cobalt. The pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter.

General procedure: To a solution containing 70 μg cobalt in a 50 ml separatory funnel, were added dilute ammonia to adjust the pH to ~ 8.9 and tris-buffer solution (2 ml; pH=8.9) and total volume made up to 10 ml. 0.1 M LCE (1 ml) was then added to it and shaken for 1 min and then chloroform (10 ml) was added, shaken and allowed to settle for 5 min. The organic phase was transferred to another separatory funnel and the aqueous phase washed with chloroform (2×5 ml). The resulting solution was stripped back into 0.1 N HCl. The aqueous phase was taken and the volume was made up to 10 ml. The absorbance value of the resulting solution was measured on the AAS using the conditions given earlier. The amount of cobalt was found out from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation: The effect of pH on the extraction with LCE shows that in the pH range 8.7–9.6 cobalt is extracted efficiently. Quantitative extraction (97.22%) of cobalt occurs with chloroform and carbon tetrachloride; the results with other solvents